

VIOLATION OF POLITENESS MAXIMS AS A CATALYST FOR TRAGEDY:

A STUDY OF AKACHI ADIMORA-EZEIGBO'S *ROSES AND BULLETS*

PATIENCE AKUNNA OSONDU

Email: patienceosondu@gmail.com

&

UMEH, IFEYINWA JULIANA

E-mail: ifeyinwaju67@gmail.com

Department of Languages & Humanities

School of General Studies

Alvan Ikoku Federal College of Education Owerri.

Abstract

Human activities are conditioned by proper use of language. The primary use of language is for communication and communication is the transmission of information from one person to another in order to elicit a response. The response may be positive or negative depending on how language is used. Positive response leads to harmonious living among people while negative one produces conflicts among individuals. For harmonious living politeness principles are important tools in language use to reduce frictions, avoid conflicts and maintain a cordial relationship among members of a speech community. When politeness is violated in an environment, agitations and conflicts erupt. This leads to tragic situations. This paper investigates the violation of politeness principles as a catalyst for tragedy in a literary text which is a fair representation of a community. It also evaluates the applicability of this principle to regulate spoken discourse. Excerpts from the text *Roses and Bullets* were collated and analysed based on Geoffery Leech's (1983) politeness maxims. From the findings the researcher discovered that so many expressions which violate the maxim of politeness principles are prevalent in the text. The study reveals that violation of politeness principles leads to many forms of tragedy-strife, rancour, agitations and even death. It therefore recommends that this conversation principle should not be violated so that the society will enjoy a harmonious and peaceful living.